

УРОКИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА С УЧЕТОМ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ И ПОТРЕБНОСТЕЙ УЧАЩИХСЯ: ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОМУ ОБУЧЕНИЮ

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***Аннотация.** В статье рассматриваются практические подходы к реализации дифференцированного обучения на уроках английского языка. Автор акцентирует внимание на необходимости учитывать индивидуальные особенности учащихся-уровень владения языком, стиль обучения, интересы и мотивацию. Описываются ключевые стратегии дифференциации: варьирование содержания, процессов и конечных продуктов обучения. Приводятся примеры адаптации заданий и методов работы в группах, позволяющих одновременно развивать сильных учащихся и поддерживать тех, кто испытывает трудности.*

Материал статьи может быть полезен преподавателям школ, стремящихся повысить эффективность и результативность обучения.

***Ключевые слова:** дифференцированное обучение, адаптация заданий, индивидуальные особенности учащихся, разноуровневые группы.*

TAILORING ENGLISH LESSONS TO LEARNERS: PRACTICAL APPROACH TO DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION

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***Abstract.** This article explores practical approaches to implementing differentiated instruction in English language lessons. The article highlights the role of differentiated instructions and the integration technology in creating inclusive learning environments. It emphasizes the importance of tailoring instruction to accommodate students' varying levels, learning styles interests, and motivation.*

Key differentiation strategies are discussed, including adapting content, processes, and learning outcomes. Examples of task modification and classroom techniques are provided, demonstrating how teachers can simultaneously support struggling students and challenge advanced learners.

This article offers practical insights that can be valuable for teachers aiming to enhance both the effectiveness and equity of their instruction.

***Key words:** learner-centered approach, diverse classroom, engaging task, differentiated learning.*

In today's diverse classroom environment the traditional one-size-fits-all approach to teaching English is no longer sufficient. Grade 8-11 students come with varying level of language proficiency (some students attend English courses, some improve their level at Summer Language Camps abroad), all of them have different learning styles and diverse cultural background.

But English State Curriculum content is general for all students, so we have to work with all of them. One of the solution is differentiated. Differentiated instruction offers a practical solution by tailoring teaching methods, content and assessment to meet individual students' needs while maintaining common learning objectives.

Differentiated instruction offers a flexible, and inclusive framework, that addresses these differences and ensures all students can succeed.

Differentiated instruction, popularized by Carol Ann Tomlinson (1999) is based on the premise, that teachers can modify content, process, product, and learning environment to meet individual needs." Differentiated instruction is simply a teacher attending to the learning needs of a particular student or small groups of students, rather than teaching a class as though all individuals in it were basically alike." [1.p.21]

It involves modifying three key elements. First one is what student learn(content), the second is how students learn (process), and the third one is how students demonstrate their learning (product). Differentiation by content- adjusting the material students learn. Differentiation by process- varying how students engage with the material. Differentiation by product-allowing different ways to demonstrate understanding. Moreover, differentiation by learning environment- creating flexible spaces that support various learning preferences. In ELT differentiation aligns with communicative and task-based approaches and promoting learner autonomy and motivation.

Process is 'how' of teaching, differentiated instruction, the way you teach reflects the learning styles and preferences of students. We can modify process by adding greater complexity or abstractness to tasks, by engaging student in critical and creative thinking, or by increasing the variety of ways in which you ask them to learn.

For instance, a class is working on comparing and contrasting two versions of "Cinderella" from different cultures. Having decided to assign tasks based on learning styles, we assign students to groups of visual, auditory and kinesthetic learners. The visual learners draw pictures of both similar and different elements of two stories. The auditory learners discuss similarities and differences between two version s with partners and prepare on oral presentation. The kinesthetic learners create 30-60 seconds scene reenactments that represent similarities and differences between two versions. At the end of the work time all groups share their ideas.

Note, that while the content is the same the ways students are able to learn or process the information is different.

Differentiated content is "what" of teaching. Curriculum content is usually determined by the school or state or education department and reflects state or national standard. Content is differentiated by concentration on the most relevant and essential concepts, processes and skills or by increasing the complexity of learning. Some students need more instruction and practice, some need less.

We differentiate content: a. when we preassess learners with appropriate activities, according to readiness b. when we give students choices about topics to explore in greater depth c. when we provide student with basic and advanced resources that match their current levels of understanding. For example, the theme of the topic "Career Planning and Future Goals", according to their level students can fill-in-the blanks CV formats with guidance, another group can compare and contrast different career path, third group write an analytical reports on skills needed for future careers.

Products are the end results of learning. It may be something tangible (brochure, model), or it may involve action, mock trial, a skit. Products reflects what students have understood and been able to apply. Students create products that match their learning strength.

All good teachers differentiate to some degree. Each time you provide a student with extra help, more time, or a modified assignment, you're differentiated instruction. So, In a differentiated classroom, the teacher acts as:

- a facilitator (organizing the learning process and guiding students),
- an observer (assessing and analyzing students' progress),

- a learning partner (creating conditions for students' active engagement in the learning process).

The goal of differentiating instruction is to increase the likelihood that students will be successful learners. A good way to enhance students' chances for success is to get to know them and to understand how they differ from one another in interests, learning preferences and pace, readiness and motivation. We can use different tools for gathering information about students' academic history, interested, preferred ways of learning, and current level of knowledge and skills by means of academic history, test results, students' work portfolios, our professional observation. We can gather additional information through students' inventories, pre-assessments, and family conferences and conversations.

Although differentiated instruction offers many benefits for language learning, it also creates several challenges in terms of students' assessment. One of them is varied level of tasks. Students are given assignments of different complexity and length. Evaluating these products with the same grade scale often feels unfair. The second one is balancing absolute and relative criteria. School standards usually demands absolute evaluation based on curriculum outcomes, at the same time, teachers are encourage to recognize students' growth, effort, and motivation.

Traditional numeric grades do not always capture language development, and comparison between students can undermine the very principle of differentiation. "Assessment always has more to do with helping students grow than with the cataloging their mistakes." [2.p. 11].

Formative assessment, effectively used, demonstrate to learners that we are listening to them, want them to grow, and are providing specific support and guidance for that growth.

To overcome these challenges, several strategies have proven effective. First, rubrics with leveled criteria allow teachers to maintain fairness while recognizing different learner levels. Combining absolute and relative assessment ensures that both curriculum outcomes and individual growth are acknowledged. Frequent formative assessment helps track progress and guide instruction before summative grading. Additionally, self- and peer-assessment tools promote learner autonomy and reduce teacher workload. Providing descriptive feedback supports motivation better than grades alone, and the use of portfolios makes long-term progress visible for students, teachers, and parents alike.

By integrating these approaches, teachers can make assessment in a differentiated English classroom more equitable, transparent, and supportive of every learner's development. Every student should see that their effort and progress matter, not only their final result, growth is measured relative to starting point, not just against one standard.

To sum up, implementing differentiated instruction in English lessons allows educators to create more inclusive and effective learning environments. Although challenges remain in assessment and classroom management, the benefits of increased learner motivation and achievement outweigh the difficulties. Future classroom practices should aim to combine differentiated strategies with formative assessment to maximize student growth.

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